

Techno-economic evaluation of biogas-fed SOFC power system integrated with biogas cleaning unit

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Abstract

Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) technology has recently raised much attention. As a promising power generation technology, the SOFC system demonstrates high electrical efficiency and great potential in decentralized energy application due to its compact configuration. Operating at high temperatures ($> 680\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), SOFC also cogenerates high-quality heat and can be integrated with different industry facilities electrically and thermally.

In the context of the Paris Agreement, more and more solutions to replace fossil fuels have been proposed, where biogas is considered as one promising alternative. Via gasification, waste biomass can be converted into fuel-rich biogas with complex composition. Unlike other fuel cell technologies, SOFC technology demonstrates high tolerance of fuel type, even with several impurities, e.g., biogas. In this case, a small scale biogas-fed SOFC power system with capacity ranging from 20 kW to 200 kW can be implemented beside the biomass gasification plant to generate both renewable electricity and heat for the plant and the household.

Raw biogas contains some contaminants, e.g., H_2S , which is harmful to the SOFC and should be kept under a safe concentration level. In this case, a biogas cleaning unit should be implemented before the SOFC system for safe operation. The biogas cleaning unit can be comprehensively integrated with the SOFC system in both electricity and heat to reduce the eventual operation expenditure (OPEX), which is seldom considered. To exploit the potential of the biogas-fed SOFC system integrated with a biogas cleaning unit, this study firstly investigated the efficiency of the SOFC power system fed with biogas from two aspects: (1) SOFC system configuration and (2) biogas type. Next, different types of biogas cleaning units will be modeled and integrated with the SOFC system. With the biogas flow rate as the decision variable, the whole integrated system will be techno-economically evaluated by applying the capital expenditure (CAPEX), operation expenditure (OPEX), and levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) as the index. Techno-economical comparison between two schemes that are with or without heat and electricity integration is performed as well.